

A RESEARCH ON DIVINE PRASANNA SASTRA

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Abstract:

The timing of event can be arrived with the help of Prassanam. In kaliyuga the planets are doing it job in different manner other than the Karagathuvas. I my research method of prasanna sastra, in the prasanna chart if lagna lord and star lord will show the bavas which related to question asked for prasannam. If it not showing the respective bavas the answer for the prasannam will not arrive. To fix timing of event for the question asked we have to look for lord of third house and eleventh house. It should be placed in position Kendra sthanam. With the help of this system we can predict whether it will happen or not. Result can be obtained when Lagna lord and Star Lord, and 3rd lord and 11th lord are in Kendra position in the Prasanna Jathaga., if Lagna is not conjunct with 3/11 Bhavas, the question should not be answered. This is the Research on Prasanna Sastra I have tried my best to get result of the Timing of event using this Prassanna Sastra. I named it as "Divine Prasanna Sastra"

Key Words: Timing of Event, Prasannam, Divine Prasanna Sastra, Marriage Prasannam, Horary Astrology, Prasanna Sastra, Event happening, Transit moon and Prasannam, Prasanna Astrology, Horary Prasannam

Prasanna Jathaga and Moon:

Manokarakan Moon should reflect the question, the nature of the question. Please show the question.

- Lord of which house?
- Which house is he in?
- Whose star is it in?
- In whose star is he in which house?
- Whose Nakshatra is the lord of which houses?
- Who is Moon in conjunction with whom?
- Of what sins are those who live together like that?
- Who sees the moon?
- Which house do the aspecting planets rule?
- Which houses do the aspecting planets belong to?

Etc. Moon will definitely reflect the nature of the question. There is no chance not to reflect like that.

- Lagna is debilitated and Moon is aspected by Saturn. Here the position of the moon should be seen. He will show the nature of the question.
- If the Moon is in Agni Tattva the matter will be difficult with the tracks
- If the Moon is in the wind aspect, things will go smoothly

Lagna Strength Rule 1 in Prasanna Jathaga: In Prasanna Jathaga, Lagna lord or ascendant Nakshatra, both, or one of the two, 3rd Bhava lord, or/and 11th lord (either one or both) must be aspected, conjoined, or conjunct in some way through a standing star.

The question can be answered only if it is connected like that. If it doesn't connect like that, there is no answer to the question. Even if Lagna lord and Lagna, or/ and 3rd lord and 11th lord are Kendras, if Lagna is not conjunct with 3/11 Bhavas, the question should not be answered. If you take it wrongly, the answer will be wrong.

For example:

- The position of Lakinadipati Prasanna in the horoscope may be 3rd or 11th bhava.
- Lagna Nakshatra lord may be 3rd or 11th Bhava.
- Lagna lord posited nakshatra lord and 3rd or 11th lord nakshatra lord can be same.
- The question and the questionable sin
- Aspecting Lagna lord or Lagna fallen star, 3rd house, 11th house, 3rd house house or 11th house house.

Prasanna Jathaga and Saturn:

If Saturn is as follows in Prasanna Jathaga, it will give delay.

- Saturn aspecting 3rd and 11th houses
- Saturn aspecting the 311 lords (If this is the case, if the lords in the Kendra at 311 are not aspected by Saturn, the work will be done through them)

- Saturn being or aspecting the Ascendant
- Saturn being with lagna lord
- Saturn should not be in 8th house from Ascendant and should not aspect 8th house.
- Saturn aspecting Moon or being with Moon
- Saturn's association with the Karaka planet relevant to the question asked
- Houses aspected by Saturn, respective lords, planets in Saturn's star, planets in Saturn's house will not work.
- If the degree in which Lagna falls in Prasanna Jathaga is the degree of Saturn in the birth horoscope of the seeker of Prasanna, the matter will be a drawn-out struggle and will not happen.
- Although Saturn is in 11th for Capricorn and Aquarius Lagna, he will not be late. Things happen together.
- Saturn will not cause delay if 3/11 lords are aspected by Karagraha of question.

Lagna Strength Rule 2 in Prasanna Jathaga:

In Prasanna Jathaga, the question should not be answered if the lagna is conjunct at the time it ends in a bhava. After some time, Prashant can be done. At the same time, if the Lagna is in the initial period, it can be beneficial.

Parivarthanai in Prasanna Jathaga:

Prasanna Jathaga is transacted once every 2 hours. There are 2 things to know about Parivarthanais in Prasanna Jathaga.

Upper level Parivarthanai:

In Prasanna Jathaga, if two planets are transiting in the same philosophy, it is called upper level transit. For example Jupiter is in Leo and Sun is in Sagittarius.

Lower Level Parivarthanai:

If the transiting planets are in different philosophies, it is a subordinate transit. Example: Saturn in Virgo and Mars in Capricorn. Or Moon in Aries and Mars in Cancer.

Definiton for Parivarthana in Prasanna Jathaga:

- If two planets are exchanged in Prasanna Jathaga, it should be decided whether or not the exchange will take place depending on the position of Sun.
- If the lagna is in the same aspect as the Sun or in a friendly aspect (eg fire+fire or fire+air) i.e. if the lagna falls in the 1st, 3rd, 5th, 7th, 9th, 11th, bhavas from the Sun, there will be no Parivarthanai. This means that the obtained Prasanna Jathaga should be used without making any changes.
- If there is an exchange in the opposite philosophy to the one in which the Sun is, i.e. if the Lagna falls in 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 bhavas from the Sun, then the transited planets will change their bhavas.
- If Sun is in Pisces, Guru is in Leo, and if Pisces is Lagna, the result should be given by placing Sun in Pisces and Jupiter in Leo.

Otherwise, if the Lagna is Mesa Lagna, transiting planets will change their sins. That is, the result should be given by keeping Sun in Leo and Guru in Pisces. When such a Parivarthanai takes place, all the planets in the same bhava with the transiting planet will become a Shera Parivarthanai. When there is a Parivarthanai like this, Rahu or Ketu is the Parivarthanai but only which planet is the Parivarthanai. That means the planet with Rahu is transitive but only Rahu. Ketu will not.

How Parivarthanai Works in Prasnanam:

For example there is a transit between Jupiter and Venus in the horoscope. And the Sun is in the water aspect, the corresponding aspect is land and water. Negative philosophy is wind and fire. Here, in Pisces/Taurus/Cancer/Virgo/Scorpio/Capricorn, there is no Parivarthanai when Prasanna ascends.

Aries/Gemini/Leo/Libra/Sagittarius/Aquarius are in the signs of Prasanna Lagna when the Parivarthanai takes place. When the exchange takes place, Venus and its companion Sun and Mercury will move to Libra. Guru will come to Pisces.

Question and Sin:

The question is which sin should be seen. For example

Mother is the 4th sin

If father has 9th sin,

For me it means Lakina Bhava

Will I pass the exam 3/11 of 6

3/11 for house building 4

When will I go home - 4/12 for laguna

7 for 3/11 when the questioner asked when he got married

My aspiration is when my father will come. 3/11 for Lakinam here

3/11 of 5 When will my son or daughter be born?

My father-in-law means Lakinam 7 husband and his father 7 and 9 sin, 3 sin. 3 for 3/11 Sins to see.

For the question like when will the post arrive, take the 3rd bhava and determine that the post or courier will arrive at the time when the lords of 3/11 join.

Missing thing or person is 4th sin

The lord of the 4th house will lose or forget the relational material belonging to that house. If the example is in Lakinam, the person who asked the question has made it disappear.

The missing object is in the direction of the house in which the 4th bhava lord is

If the lord of the 4th house is malefic or not subor, 1 4 5 7 9 houses, the person will come.

3 6 He will come even if there is a malefic planet in 11

3 6 If there is a benefic planet in 11 the person is dead

If Lagna lord and 7th lord are together then missing object will be found.

Who won't get things done:

Things will not happen through houses aspected by Saturn, respective lords, planets in Saturn's star, planets in Saturn's house.

Which Planets will done the job.

- 3/11 lords will get things done
- Planets in 3/11 lords saras
- 3/11 houses or their lords are aspected by Saturn, 3/11 lords are in 8th to Lagna, 1/7 lords are not aspected by Saturn.
- A planet in Lakinadhipati's Nakshatra will also complete the task

Results of Timing Event:

To know when it will happen depends on the nature of the question and can also be known by the placement of 3/11 lords. Important Rule in Timing of Event is 3/11 lords

- If transiting planets like Sun, Mars, Moon etc. come as 3/11 lords things will go well.
- If 3/11 lords are in same house then things will go together
- If the 3/11 lords are in Kendra, it will happen (successfully resolved)
- If lords of 3/11 fall on 2/12, delay by hours
- If 3/11 lords fall on 3/11 then there will be delay in counting days
- May or may not happen if 3/11 lords come in 5/9
- If lords of 3/11 come with 6/8 will not happen

When will the event happen for Prasannam Question, The Lagna Rasinathan and Lagna Nathan of the Horoscope placed together can give the answer to the interpretation question based on the sign of how they are located in the horoscope. That is,

- If 1, 7, 4, 10 comes as Kendra, it will happen together
- If it is 2/12: It should be said that the hour is passing.
- If it falls on 3/11: Happens in days
- If it falls on 5/9: Happens in weeks//months
- If it comes to 6/8: Not going to happen

We can answer with that.

The Base of Timing of Event Calculations:

To find the timing event, we must know the period ruled by the significator planet. There are so many types of dasha systems. But I found the Vimshottari dasha most reliable. This system is based on the longitude of the Moon. The total dasha period is 120 years. The ancient sages found out the life of human beings to be 120 years. Now it is supported by scientists in the present day. They have tested a particular part of the body, and ascertained that it can work for 120 years. Now they are also in agreement that the maximum life of a person can be up to 120 years old.

The total period of 120 years has been allotted to 9 grahas, I will use word “**Graha**” which is different than the word “planet”. “Planets” and “Stars” are the words used for heavenly bodies. Rahu and Ketu are grahas, but they are not planets. “Graha” means sources of energy, attraction, so it may be a distincton.

There are inner grahas and outer grahas. “Inner grahas” means grahas between the Earth and the Sun, which includes the Sun, Mercury, Venus and the Moon. Ketu is also included in the inner grahas. Mars, Jupiter Saturn are outer grahas, and Rahu is treated as an outer graha as well. 120 years are divided in two equal parts of 60 years each and allotted to inner and outer grahas.

Starting from Revati, which is ruled by Mercury, then Ketu, Venus, Sun, and Moon, allotting 17 years, 7yrs, 20 yrs, 6 yrs, and 10 years respectively for a total of 60 years . Then Outer Grahas, Mars 7 years, Rahu 18 years, Jupiter 16 years, Saturn 19 years for a total of another 60 years. (See Figure 1)

Inner Grahas	
Mercury	17 years
Ketu	7 years
Venus	20 years
Sun	6 years
Moon	10 years
Total Years	60
Outer Grahas	
Mars	7 years
Rahu	18 years
Jupiter	16 years
Saturn	19 years
Total Years	60

The periods, as shown in Figure 1, are known as Mahadashas (Main Periods). It is further sub divided into sub periods. The division for each of these subperiod planets is in proportion to its Mahadasha period. The first division is always that of the Mahadasha Lord. The sub period can be found from the following formula:

Let M = Mahadasha period

Let S = the sub lord of the mahadasha period

Let s = result of sub period in decimal years, which can be converted into months and days.

The formula now becomes: $s = M \times S$ divided by 120

For example, we want to find the sub period of Mercury in the Main period of Saturn. If we look at the table in Figure 1, you can see that Saturn (M) = 19 years and Mercury (S) = 17 years.

$$s = M \times S \text{ divided by } 120$$

$$s = 19 \times 17 \text{ divided by } 120$$

$$s = 2.6916666$$

This converts into 2 years 8 months and 9 days.

- However, there is an easier way to do this, by dividing the original formula by 10 instead of 12. This will automatically give you the number of months. Let’s see.

$$\text{Number of months} = M \times S \text{ divided by } 10$$

$$\text{Number of months} = 19 \times 17 \text{ divided by } 10$$

$$\text{Number of months} = 32.3$$

The 32.3 means 32 months and .3 of a month or $3 \times 3 = 9$ days

We can now see that 32 months = 2 years and 8 months (plus the 9 days), which comes to the same thing as the

first formula where we divided by 12.

- This can be done orally also, but we must know the mahadasha period first.

For example, let's take Rahu. If we want to take the sub period of Rahu in the Mahadasha period of Rahu, we will have this:

RAHU Mahadasha = 18

Rahu Subperiod = 18

Total = 324 (leave out the 4)

Leave out the last digit, which is 4, so that the remainder is 32. These are the number of months, which then converts to 2 years and 8 months. Now multiply the last digit of the number 324 by 3. It gives the days. Therefore, the subperiod of Rahu in the Rahu Mahadasha = 2 years 8 months, 12 days.

- Mars sub in Mars main = $7 \times 7 = 49 =$ four months and 27 days. $49 \div 10 = 4.9$ which equals 4 months and 27 (9 X 3) days.
- Sun sub in Moon main = $6 \times 10 = 60 =$ six months and 0 days. From the above equation one can find the sub period of any planet.
- Now suppose the main period of Venus starts from the 1st of Jan., 1980. It lasts for 20 years. Now we have to find the sub period of Mars in Venus main.

Add the total years of Venus + Sun + Moon up to Mars = $20 + 6 + 10 = 36$.

Now we have to find the start of the Mars sub period. So we multiply 36 by 20 (the main period of Venus) $36 \times 20 = 720$ leaving out the last digit which gives us 72 (months) = 6 years. The last digit of 720 stands for days which gives us zero days.

This means that the Mars sub period will start 6 years after 1st Jan 1980 which is the 1st Jan 1986. And the Mars period will be $7 \times 20 = 140 =$ one year 2 months. Similarly we can find the sub period of any planet in the main or Mahadasha period of any planet. The Vimshottari Mahadasha is based upon the constellation of the Moon, in which it is situated and uses the angular distance of each Nakshatra, which is 13 deg. 20 min.

Conversion Table	
Aries	0°
Taurus	30°
Gemini	60°
Cancer	90°
Leo	120°
Virgo	150°
Libra	180°
Scorpio	210°
Sagittarius	240°
Capricorn	270°
Aquarius	300°
Pisces	330°

If we want to find the Main constellation period from the Moon's longitude, first convert it to degrees, divide it by 120, then multiply the decimal portion by 9. The Dasha system is based on the Hindu Calendar which has approximately 360 days (average). In actuality, the Hindu calendar is based on the Moon and the English calendar is based on the Sun, which contains 365 days with one day added for every leap year. In the Hindu calendar some months are added or subtracted. This is known as Adhik mas (additional month) and kshaya mas (deleted month) and matches the Sun's transit. It may be difficult to calculate the dasha system actually as per the Hindu calendar. It is much easier to follow the English Calendar for this. The maximum difference may be 18 days, if we follow the English calendar.

Nakshatra #	Degrees	Nakshatra	Ruled By
1	00°AR 00' - 13°AR 20'	Aswini	Ketu
2	13°AR 20' - 26°AR 40'	Bharani	Venus
3	26°AR 40' - 10°TA 00'	Krittika	Sun
4	10°TA 00' - 23°TA 20'	Rohini	Moon
5	23°TA 20' - 06°GE 40'	Mrigishira	Mars
6	06°GE 40' - 20°GE 00'	Ardra	Rahu
7	20°GE 00' - 03°CA 20'	Purnavasru	Jupiter
8	03°CA 20' - 16°CA 40'	Pushyami	Saturn
9	16°CA 40' -- 00°LE 00'	Aslesha	Mercury
10	00°LE 00' -- 13°LE 20'	Magha	Ketu
11	13°LE 20' -- 26°LE 40'	Purva Phalguni	Venus

12	26°LE 40' -- 10°VI 00'	Uttara Phalguni	Sun
13	10°VI 00' --- 23°VI 20'	Hasta	Moon
14	23°VI 20 ---- 06°LI 40'	Chitra	Mars
15	06°LI 40' ---- 20°LI 00'	Swati	Rahu
16	20°LI 00' -- 03°SC 20'	Vishakha	Jupiter
17	03°SC 20' - 16°SC 40'	Anuradha	Saturn
18	16°SC 40' - 00°SA 00'	Jyeshtha	Mercury
19	00°SA 00' - 13°SA 20'	Mula	Ketu
20	13°SA 20' - 26°SA 40'	Purvashadha	Venus
21	26°SA 40' - 10°CP 00'	Uttarashadha	Sun
22	10°CP 00' - 23°CP 20'	Shravana	Moon
23	23°CP 20' - 06°AQ 40'	Dhanishtha	Mars
24	06°AQ 40' - 20°AQ 00'	Satabhisha	Rahu
25	20°AQ 00' --- 03°PI 20'	Purva Bhadra	Jupiter
26	03°PI 20' ---- 16°PI 40'	Uttara Bhadra	Saturn
27	16°PI 40' --- 00°AR 00'	Revati	Mercury

Nature of Question:

To know when the question will happen when we decide for ourselves whether it will happen in days or months

- Today means to move Lagna (24 hrs).
- Days means moving the moon
- Moon should move Sun
- If the year means Guru should be moved.

When will happen:

- 3/11 Lords Nakshatra comes as Upanakshatra when the thing happens.
- Or the 3rd lord and the 11th lord, from where they are, however many sins need to move to the 11th house, the thing will happen after the completion of as many minutes, hours, days, months and years.
- If 3/11 lords are in same house then 11th house from that house is required only once.
- If 3/11 lords are aspected in 12th to the ascendant then subtract one from the other.
- If the 11th lord is in the 11th house then things will happen even if the Lagna is 6/8.
- If the Sun is alone in the 11th and Saturn is not aspected, the thought will happen with it

Saturn Sighting Timing:

- Viewing lord Saturn 2 minutes hour day week month year
- Seeing Shani Bhava 5 minutes hour day week month year
- If in the essence of Saturn, two and a half minutes, or hour, or day, or month or year should be added.

Conclusion:

Prasanna Jathaga is transacted once every 2 hours. There are 2 things to know about Parivarthanais in Prasanna Jathaga. We will get answer for the question with the help of third and eleventh Lord will help us to arrived the timing of event for prasnannam question. Therefore if Prasanna lagna lord and star lord of the ascendant will show us bavas connected to question then the 3 and 11 house lord gives us result of the Timing of the event.

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